

RHYTHMIC PRECIPITATION OF SILVER CHLORIDE IN GELATIN TANNED WITH CHROMIUM CHLORIDE.

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On allowing a highly concentrated silver nitrate solution to diffuse into a gelatin gel, tanned with CrCl_3 of such concentrations that all the available Cl' is combined with the gelatin, in a test tube, dirty white rings of AgCl have been obtained. The study of the influence of concentration of gelatin, CrCl_3 , and AgNO_3 on the dimensions of the rings and interspaces shows that they behave differently from those of $\text{Ag}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ rings in gelatin mixed with $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.

Up to this time the reaction studied with regard to Liesegang rings are such that the reacting ion in the gel is quite free and not in any way bound up with the gel substance. The abnormal behaviour of chrome-tanned gelatin with regard to its solubility and muta-rotation as observed by Kuntzel and Boensel (*Collegium*, 1936, 576) throwing reflection on the theory of tanning of hides and adsorption experiments by Cameron and McLanlyhlin (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 961) show that both the cations and anions of chromium salts become chemically combined with gelatin.

Object of the present work is to see how the Cl' ion of CrCl_3 , supposed to be chemically combined with gelatin molecule, influences the formation of silver chloride layers when a highly concentrated silver nitrate solution is diffused in the gelatin, tanned with dilute chromium chloride. The authors have studied the influence of change of concentrations of chromium chloride, silver nitrate and gelatin on the nature and width of the silver chloride rings as well as their interspaces.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The preliminary experiments revealed the conditions and the relative concentrations of gelatin, CrCl_3 , and AgNO_3 suitable for obtaining the rings at 25° (Table I). The concentrations of CrCl_3 chosen were such as may contain Cl just sufficient to combine with gelatin taken in each test tube.

TABLE I.

Gelatin.	CrCl_3 .	AgNO_3 .	Minimum age of gel.	Minimum time for rings to develop.
20 c.c. of 3 to 4.5%	1 c.c. of 5 to 7%	5 c.c. of 4 to 6%	24 hours	11 days,

Occasional exposure to day light for a few minutes only was also found to be essential in addition.

Test tubes of the same dimensions were used for the formation of AgCl rings. Gelatin solution (20 c.c.) was introduced in a test tube and CrCl_3 solution (1 c.c.) of the required concentration added to it and mixed well by shaking; the mixture was allowed to set to a gel in an air thermostat at $25^\circ (\pm 1^\circ)$ for 24 hours. The required AgNO_3 solution (5 c.c.) was then poured at the top of gel along the side of the test tubes taking care not to disturb the gel. All the test tubes were allowed to remain in the rack in the air thermostat free from light for eleven days. Every alternate day, day light was admitted into the thermostat for five minutes. After eleven days a set of three test tubes was taken out each time carefully and immediately photographed after placing in a rack kept at a fixed distance from the camera.

The combining weights of gelatin as a base as well as an acid, determined by conductometric titration of a 5% solution of gelatin against $N\text{-HCl}$ and $N\text{-NaOH}$ respectively, were found to be 1111 and 1428 respectively; from this the quantities of Cl' and Cr''' in combination with gelatin as well as in the free state were calculated (Tables II and III).

TABLE II.

Gelatin.	Cl' available in tubes (containing $\text{CrCl}_3, 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$).			Cl' required for combination.
	7%.	6%.	5%.	
3.0%	0.0220 g.	0.0189 g.	0.0157 g.	0.0192 g
3.5	"	"	"	0.0224
4.0	"	"	"	0.0256
4.5	"	"	"	0.0288

Free Cl' in case of 3% gelatin might be present in the form of HCl , since CrCl_3 may be getting hydrolysed to $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ and HCl , the former being colloiddally adsorbed on the gel.

TABLE III.

Gelatin.	Cr''' available in tubes (containing $\text{CrCl}_3, 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$)			Cr required for combination.
	7%.	6%.	5%	
3.0%	0.0108 g.	0.0092 g.	0.0077 g.	0.0073 g.
3.5	"	"	"	0.0085
4.0	"	"	"	0.0097
4.5	"	"	"	0.0109

A comparison of Tables II and III reveals that Cr^{+++} is free in such test tubes as contain no free Cl^- ; in such cases Cr might be present as $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$.

DISCUSSION.

On allowing a highly concentrated AgNO_3 solution to diffuse into a gelatin gel, tanned with CrCl_3 , of such concentrations that all the available Cl^- is combined with the gelatin in a test tube, dirty white rings of AgCl and black brown spaces, quite distinct from the chrome-tanned gel, have been obtained in the lower zone of the precipitate.

The points worth noting in our case are (i) that the interspaces between the rings and the width of the ring itself go on decreasing in downward direction; (ii) the width of the ring increases and interspaces decrease with decrease in concentration of gelatin; (iii) interspaces, however, increase with increasing concentration of AgNO_3 and decrease with increasing concentration of CrCl_3 .

The above observations show that rhythmic precipitation of AgCl in gelatin tanned with CrCl_3 takes place in quite a different manner from that of $\text{Ag}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in gelatin mixed with $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. In both cases nearly the same concentrations of gelatin and AgNO_3 have been found suitable for producing the rings. The principal points of difference between the two cases appear to be (i) that the $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions reacting with AgNO_3 remain free, while the Cl^- ions in this case remain almost totally in combination with gelatin (*cf.* Table III); (ii) that the structure and physical properties of gel in tanned conditions are different from those in ordinary state as observed by Kuntzel and Boensel (*loc. cit.*). But since Gore (*Kolloid Z.*, 1936, 76, 193) has been able to get rhythmic precipitation in non-gelatinous media such as $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ precipitates, the responsibility of the change in the structure of the gel in such abnormal behaviour of AgCl rings, is therefore, ruled out.

It has been noted above that after occasional short exposure to daylight, the colour of the interspace in our case was brown black, quite different from that of chrome-tanned gel, and that on continuous exposure to day light the colour of rings and interspaces became uniform; from this we conclude that in our case a layer of coagulated AgCl is followed by a layer of peptised AgCl , as observed by Dhar and Chatterji (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 41) in case of mercuric iodide rings. The authors feel that gelatin chloride gets partially ionised at lower pH value (3.4) as observed

by Hitschock (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1922, 235, 383); Sokolon and Kaja (*Kolloid Z.*, 1935, 70, 314) have found that when chromium salts combine with gelatin pH value falls rapidly. Since only free Cl^- ions migrate upwards to meet the diffusing $AgNO_3$, while combined chloride remains bound in the molecule, no space in the gel is totally free from chloride and hence the clear gel does not succeed the precipitated layer. The $AgNO_3$ reacting with free Cl^- ions forms $AgCl$ sol, while that reacting with free Cl^- ions forms $AgCl$ precipitate. But until $AgNO_3$ solution reaches a high dilution on diffusion, $AgCl$ sol is coagulated by $AgNO_3$; hence the ring formation of $AgCl$ takes place in the lower zone of the precipitate.

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